

Social

A TOOL CONSTRUCTION AND STANDARDIZATION OF PARA-ACADEMIC ACTIVITIES

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Abstract

In the present study, Para-Academic Activities scale has been constructed and standardized of the Higher Secondary Students. This scale consists of 75 statements. The simple random sample technique was used for this study. The sample consists of 100 Higher Secondary Students are randomly selected from the Thiruvannamalai Districts. The 't' value was used to standardize the tool and finally 36 statements were retained for the final study.

Keywords: Para-Academic Activities; Higher Secondary.

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1. Introduction

Para-academic activities are those activities that enhancement of the teaching learning process. For example, organization of clubs is one of the Para-academic activities; attending science and social science fairs are also a Para-academic activity in the teaching of science or social. Science or Social quiz activity is also a Para-academic activity, which enhancements the teaching-learning process. Para-academic activity has a vital role in the teaching of science or social.

Para-academic activities are now considered to be an intrinsic part of the education endeavor in a secondary school. Till recently, these were called extra-curricular activities. But now these have been recognized as a part of regular curriculum for the complete education of the students. In fact, curricular and Para-academic activities are now considered complementary to each other, both deserving equal weight and emphasis in the total program of the secondary schools.

Operational Definition of the Terms

Para-academic activities mean it is to be an intrinsic part of the education endeavor in a secondary school or college as well as, these was called extra-curricular activities or co-curricular activities. But now these have been recognized as a part of our regular curriculum for the complete education of the students. In fact, curricular and Para-academic activities are now considered complementary to each other, both deserving equal weight and emphasis in the total program of the secondary schools. Such Para-academic activities are “ visits to museum, zoo and mathematics, computer, science and social fairs and exhibitions, field trips to the historical and geographical places, coins exhibition, scientific hobbies, science and social clubs, and Indian association for extra: curricular activities”.

Pilot Study

The investigator has broadly thinking for my research and a few readymade or standardized tools available on the society but investigator feels, accurate scale needed to do my research on perfectly. So, the investigator has prepared 75 statements of Para-academic activities scale, with help of the guide and it has five dimensions (Academic development, Interest development, Attitude development, Social development and Health and Hygiene development). As well as, before went to pilot study the investigator got it feedback and suggestions from concern subject experts. Finally, the investigator has conducted pilot study; this study to represent all the characteristics of population, probability sampling technique was used. For the selection of schools and students, simple random sampling technique was used. 100 students were taken as the sample from four higher secondary schools in the Thiruvannamalai District.

Scoring Procedure

The investigator has constructed and standardization of Para-academic activities scale scoring procedure is YES or NO type. All statements are positive and each statement is having YES or No response, if response is ‘YES’ given one mark, if response is ‘NO’ given zero mark.

Items Selection

According to Edwards (1957), “the value of ‘t’ is a measure of the extent to which a given item differentiates between the high and low groups. If the ‘t’ value is equal to or greater than 1.96, it indicates that the average response of the high and low groups to a statement differs significantly, provided there are 27 or more subjects in the high group and also in the low group”.

The ‘t’ value of all the 75 items were obtained to select the items for the final draft. Out of 75 items, 36 items were having ‘t’ value more than 1.96 and 39 items were deleted. They are given in table -1.

Item selected for the final draft of the Para-academic activities based on their ‘t’ value between upper and lower group:

Table 1:

Item Numbers	't' Value	Item selected*	Item No. in the final Draft of PAA
1	2.180	S	1
2	1.087	-	-
3	1.004	-	-
4	3.317	S	2
5	2.068	S	3
6	1.000	-	-
7	1.000	-	-
8	1.000	-	-
9	0.000	-	-
10	2.375	S	4
11	2.594	S	5
12	0.869	-	-
13	1.408	-	-
14	2.324	S	6
15	1.000	-	-
16	0.000	-	-
17	0.869	-	-
18	4.561	S	7
19	1.600	-	-
20	2.750	S	8
21	2.750	S	9
22	1.408	-	-
23	2.934	S	10
24	0.585	-	-
25	2.294	S	11
26	3.519	S	12
27	0.000	-	-
28	3.581	S	13
29	5.701	S	14
30	2.750	S	15
31	0.585	-	-
32	3.606	S	16
33	1.941	-	-
34	2.451	S	17
35	0.268	-	-
36	1.600	-	-
37	1.000	-	-
38	2.000	S	18
39	0.462	-	-
40	0.691	-	-
41	1.749	-	-
42	1.185	-	-

43	2.153	S	19
44	2.675	S	20
45	1.000	-	-
46	0.288	-	-
47	1.147	-	-
48	2.252	S	21
49	1.654	-	-
50	1.004	-	-
51	2.126	S	22
52	2.126	S	23
53	1.803	-	-
54	3.309	S	24
55	1.363	-	-
56	2.473	S	25
57	3.309	S	26
58	2.431	S	27
59	1.306	-	-
60	1.442	-	-
61	1.442	-	-
62	1.442	-	-
63	0.000	-	-
64	3.309	S	28
65	1.537	-	-
66	3.278	S	29
67	2.750	S	30
68	2.431	S	31
69	0.270	-	-
70	2.153	S	32
71	2.726	S	33
72	2.068	S	34
73	1.749	-	-
74	2.590	S	35
75	2.675	S	36

S= selected*

Here, the investigator has mentioned 36 selected statements only.

Table 2:

S. No.	Statements	Yes	No
Academic Development			
1.	I use library for my subject related references.		
2.	I have drawn important of subject content and sub-content in charts and have placed in my class room.		
3.	During holidays, I use to go to special classes for studying school subjects.		
4.	As I study for my exams, I could not exhibit my talents.		

5.	I use to go for education tour arranged by my school.		
6.	I read newspaper daily.		
Interest Development			
7.	I wish to participate in school cultural activities.		
8.	I would like to collect ancient coins and postal stamps of various countries.		
9.	I like to read literatures.		
10.	My parents do not allow me to have pets at home.		
11.	I decorate my room with toys and posters of natural scenery.		
12.	I like to tell the stories to others.		
13.	I Would like to be a pupil leader in class or school.		
14.	I wish to share the awareness issues, with my class mates.		
15.	I like to gather the handicraft items.		
Attitude Development			
16.	Getting good marks in examination will develop positive interest towards skill development.		
17.	I am able to balance my sports and academic performance because of my teachers and parents encouragement		
18.	Most of the schools do not give attention to sports and cultural activities as serious as academic results.		
19.	I will succeed in art filed (Story/ Poetry/ literature) and reach ultimate position in them.		
20.	I feel that the success in sports, gives me a confidence towards life.		
Social Development			
21.	In holidays, I used to go out with my friends for chatting.		
22.	I would like to go to my native place in holidays, to meet my Relatives and Friends.		
23.	I want to involve in social service to serve the poor people.		
24.	Participating in games surely build an attitude of being together.		
25.	I participate in all religious festivals of my friends.		
26.	I interestingly participate in social awareness program conducted by school.		
27.	Educational excursion helps to learn the art and cultures of other parts of our nation.		
Health & Hygiene Development			
28.	I believe doing yoga gives mental and spiritual strength to me.		
29.	If I am not well, I keep myself away from my class mates.		
30.	I used to play my favorite games whenever I have leisure time.		
31.	In my school, often conduct the health check up camps for students.		
32.	Many times I skip food while playing games interestingly.		
33.	I have healthy mental attitude towards opposite gender, because I am Friendly to all.		
34.	A safe and clean toilet facility is there in my school.		
35.	During rainy seasons, I place awareness advertisements in school campus.		
36.	In my school, they provide purified water to every child.		

Reliability

The reliability of the tool was measured by split-half method. Split a test into two halves, usually the odd-numbered items and the even-numbered items, and then correlate the scores obtained by each person on one half with those obtained by each person on the other. This procedure, which yields an estimate called the split-half reliability, enables a research to determine whether the halves of a test are measure the same quality or characteristic. The obtained correlation coefficient (r_1) is then entered into Spearman-Brown formula to calculate the whole test reliability (r_2). The sample size is 100. The investigator has found reliability coefficient of correlation is 0.88. These coefficients of correlation suggest that the Para-academic activities tool possess reliability for continue this research work.

Validity

Validity reveals the merits of our measurement. This Para-academic activities scale has five dimensions (Academic development, Interest development, Attitude development, Social development and Health and Hygiene development). It was given to the concern subject (Education, Sociology and Psychology) experts in order to find out its content validity. The experts granted that the items in the scale provided adequate coverage of the concept do to the work.

Conclusion

The investigator is hopeful that this scale would be helpful to measure Para-Academic Activities the level of the higher secondary students. Hence, this tool will be very useful for the investigator to measure to what extent the level of Para-Academic Activities is in the Higher Secondary Students and it may be utilized and extended in the same for the future researchers.

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